

HYDRIDES OF IRON

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Hydrides of the bi- and trivalent iron have been prepared in a similar way as hydrides of nickel and cobalt. Properties of iron hydrides have been studied and dissociation products of the iron hydrides have been determined and heats of formation of the hydrides calculated from the dissociation pressure at different temperatures.

In two previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 213; 1946, 23, 61) the preparation and properties of the hydrides of nickel and cobalt have been described. Following exactly the same method of preparation, the hydrides of bi- and trivalent iron have been prepared. When finely powdered anhydrous ferrous chloride suspended in dry ether is treated with an ether solution of phenyl magnesium bromide in a stream of dry hydrogen, a dark grey precipitate of iron dihydride separates. The reaction is supposed to take place according to the equation,

Similarly when a solution of anhydrous FeCl_3 in dry ether interacts with PhMgBr solution in presence of dry hydrogen, a black precipitate of FeH_3 separates slowly. The reaction in this case is as follows :

For every gram of ferrous chloride 100 c.c. of dry ether and 50 c.c. of ethereal solution of PhMgBr containing 0.1 mol. of magnesium were used for the reaction. As soon as PhMgBr was introduced, the colour of the suspension began to change and finally it became dark grey. The reaction took about 13 to 14 hours to complete. The preparations were carried out at 0° , 15° and 25° by immersing the reaction flask in a suitable bath maintained at the required temperatures, and in some cases hydrogen was passed for a very long time after the reaction was complete. When experiment was over, a small quantity of the substance was removed and its composition determined in the following manner : A small quantity of the substance was introduced into a small flask fitted with a dropping funnel and a delivery tube which was connected to a Hempel's burette. A measured volume of dilute sulphuric acid was introduced into the flask through the dropping funnel and the evolved gas was collected. The hydride decomposed quantitatively, and the volume of hydrogen evolved was obtained by subtracting the volume of the liquid introduced from the total volume of the gas collected. The solution of the iron salt was evaporated to dryness and gently ignited to burn off the organic matter. The iron oxide thus formed was dissolved again in dilute sulphuric acid and the iron precipitated as hydroxide and weighed as oxide. From the weight of the oxide the weight of iron in the hydride was calculated. A large number of preparations was made at each temperature and the product obtained in each case was analysed and the results agreed quite closely. Some typical results for each temperature are recorded below.

TABLE I
Compound : FeH_2

Temp.	Time of passing H_2 .	Wt. of Fe.	Volume of H_2 (N. T. P.) obs.	Vol. of H_2 from hydride.	Ratio Fe/H.	Composition
0°	15 hrs.	0.0819g.	68.4 c.c.	34.2 c.c.	1 : 2.07	FeH_2
0	20	0.1084	91.5	45.7	1 : 2.05	..
15	13	0.0950	79.2	39.6	1 : 2.06	..
15	25	0.1204	94.4	47.2	1 : 1.93	..
25	17	0.0795	61.4	30.7	1 : 1.97	..
25	30	0.1625	130.8	65.4	1 : 2.03	..

Trihydride of iron was likewise prepared from anhydrous ferric chloride. As anhydrous ferric chloride is soluble in ether a definite volume of its solution containing a known weight of the salt was taken in the flask and the requisite amount of freshly prepared phenyl magnesium bromide solution was dropped in and pure and dry hydrogen was passed through the vessel. The reaction took about 5 hours to complete. After the completion of the reaction the hydride separated out as a black mass. The preparation of the trihydride was also carried out at various temperatures and hydrogen passed for varying lengths of time. The composition of each product was determined in the manner described above. A large number of preparations was made at each temperature and the product obtained in each case was analysed and the composition of the hydride was found to be the same in each case. Some typical results for the product obtained at each temperature are recorded below.

TABLE II
Compound : FeH_3

Temp.	Time of passing H_2 .	Wt. of Fe.	Volume of H_2 (N. T. P.) obs.	Vol. of H_2 from hydride.	Ratio Fe/H.	Composition.
0°	4 hrs.	0.0799 g.	79.5 c.c.	47.7 c.c.	1 : 3.00	FeH_3
0	10	0.0680	68.0	40.8	1 : 3.08	..
15	5	0.1504	142.7	85.6	1 : 2.90	..
15	15	0.1385	136.6	81.9	1 : 2.97	..
25	8	0.1860	180.0	108.0	1 : 2.95	..
25	20	0.1693	168.7	95.1	1 : 3.06	..

It is interesting to note the difference between the action of water on the hydrides of nickel and cobalt and those of iron. In the case of cobalt and nickel hydrides, water liberates hydrogen and the metals are separated, which react with acids liberating an equal volume of hydrogen and are converted into the salts of the acids used. As regards the iron hydrides, the first part of the reaction—liberation of hydrogen and separation of the metal—is similar, but the finely-divided iron which separates reacts further with water forming hydroxides of the metal with evolution

of hydrogen, so that no further hydrogen is evolved on the addition of an acid. That metallic iron first separates out when the hydride is treated with water and then the finely-divided iron at once combines with the (OH) group of water to form the hydroxides $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ is shown by the fact that by the action of water on the two hydrides four atoms of hydrogen are liberated per molecule of the dihydride and five atoms of hydrogen per molecule of the trihydride. The reactions of water on the two hydrides may well be represented by the equations :

The dissociation pressure of the two hydrides were determined at different temperatures. For this purpose the hydrides were repeatedly washed with dry ether. They were then dried by heating to 25° in a current of hydrogen. The dry hydrides thus obtained still contained traces of magnesium salts as impurities. Measurements of dissociation pressures were repeated several times with different samples of the hydrides, and as the results were reproducible within 2 mm, it was clear that the traces of impurities did not vitiate the results to any great extent.

The apparatus used and the arrangements made have been fully described in the paper on cobalt hydrides (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

The temperature—dissociation pressure curves shown in Figs. 1 and 2 are the mean of several sets of experiments. In Fig. 1 the upper curve is for FeH_2 which breaks into FeH completely between 53° and 55.6° , the region indicated by the dotted line. The transition point lies in the dotted region. The composition of the second solid phase has been found by analysis and corresponds to the formula FeH .

Similarly in Fig. 2 the upper curve is for FeH_3 which breaks completely into FeH in the dotted region between 58° and 60.2° and the lower curve is for the

monohydride FeH which has also been analytically verified. The two lower curves of Figs. 1 and 2 have been found to be exactly one and the same indicating that the two hydrides FeH_2 and FeH_3 break up directly into FeH.

The composition of the second solid phase formed by the decomposition of FeH_2 and FeH_3 has been determined by analysis of the product formed at various temperatures up to 150° . One typical result for each temperature is recorded below.

TABLE III
Starting substance : FeH_2

Temp. of bath.	Wt. of Fe.	Vol. of H_2 (N. T. P.) obs.	Vol. of H_2 from hydride.	Ratio Fe/H.	Composition.
70°	0.1238 g.	72.6 c.c.	24.2 c.c.	1 : 0.98	FeH
100	0.0809	47.4	15.8	1 : 0.96	..
130	0.1610	100.9	33.6	1 : 1.04	..
150	0.1991	123.0	41.0	1 : 1.03	..

TABLE IV
Starting substance : FeH_3

Temp. of bath.	Wt. of Fe.	Vol. of H_2 (N. T. P.) obs.	Vol. of H_2 from hydride.	Ratio Fe/H.	Composition.
70°	0.1239 g.	74.0 c.c.	24.7 c.c.	1 : 1.01	FeH
100	0.1345	79.5	26.5	1 : 0.99	..
130	0.1680	103.2	34.4	1 : 1.03	..
150	0.1145	70.0	23.3	1 : 1.02	..

It will be seen that the hydride FeH is stable up to 150° . It is not possible to measure the dissociation pressure of the monohydride above 100° on account of difficulty in maintaining the temperature constant within reasonable limits.

The dissociation pressure of the monohydride, FeH, was determined in the following manner: FeH_2 or FeH_3 was decomposed by heating it just above its transition temperature. The hydrogen evolved was removed by a Töppler pump and the substance allowed to cool. The dissociation pressure of this substance was measured at various temperatures starting from the room temperature to about 100° . Several sets of measurements were made and the pressure—temperature graphs were found to be identical in each case. The mean values of the dissociation pressures at particular temperatures for the three hydrides are recorded below.

TABLE V

Compound : FeH₂

Temp.	Press.	1/T (abs).	log ₁₀ p
30.5°	4.50 cm.	0.003295	0.6532
35.8	5.86	0.003238	0.7679
40.7	7.10	0.003188	0.8513
45.7	8.43	0.003138	0.9258
50.6	9.90	0.003090	0.9956
53.0	10.60	0.003067	1.0253

TABLE VI

Compound : FeH₃

Temp.	Press.	1/T (abs).	log ₁₀ p.
35.2°	5.20 cm.	0.003245	0.7160
40.4	6.80	0.003191	0.8325
45.3	8.02	0.003142	0.9355
50.8	11.10	0.003088	1.0453
55.3	13.50	0.003046	1.1303
58.0	15.05	0.003021	1.1776

TABLE VIII

Compound : FeH

Temp.	Press.	1/T(abs).	log ₁₀ p.	Temp.	Press.	1/T(abs).	log ₁₀ p.
33.3°	1.85 cm.						
41.2	4.20	0.003183	0.6232	70.2°	17.80 cm.	0.002913	1.2504
50.8	7.00	0.003088	0.8451	75.0	20.80	0.002874	1.3181
55.6	9.10	0.003043	0.9590	80.1	23.80	0.002832	1.3766
60.2	11.80	0.003001	1.0719	85.1	27.20	0.002792	1.4346
65.4	14.50	0.002955	1.1614	89.0	29.80	—	—

Iron dihydride is a crystalline, dark grey substance which is fairly stable under ether below 5°. It decomposes in moist air but in dry air the rate of decomposition is slow. It is decomposed quantitatively by water, alcohol or dilute acids. Iron trihydride is a jet black, granular substance. Its other properties are similar to the dihydride. Slight organic impurities are produced during the course of the preparation of these hydrides. The densities of FeH₂ and FeH₃ with respect to ether have been experimentally determined and have been found to be 0.335 at 30° and 0.101 at 25° respectively. Iron monohydride is granular, grey substance and is comparatively stable than the di- and the trihydrides. It is also quantitatively decomposed by dilute acids, water and alcohol.

In the reactions: $2\text{FeH}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Fe} + \text{H}_2$; $\text{FeH}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{FeH} + \text{H}_2$ and $2\text{FeH} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Fe} + \text{H}_2$, the forward reactions with increasing temperatures take only a few hours to reach the equilibrium at a particular temperature, but the rate of the backward reaction is extremely slow.

The heat of formation of the three hydrides were calculated from the dissociation pressure—temperature data by the help of the Clapeyron—Clausius equation. From Fig. 3 in which $\log_{10} p$ is plotted against $(1/T) 10^3$ the values of the heat of formation of the three hydrides were calculated with respect to several points on the three straight lines and the mean values of the heat of formation over a range of temperature from 30° to the transition temperature in the case of FeH_2 and FeH_3 and up to about 100° for FeH are given below :

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to FeH , FeH_3 and FeH_2 .

FeH	=	10.770 cal.
FeH_3	=	9.365 ..
FeH_2	=	7.178 ..

Further work on these types of compounds is in progress. In conclusion we wish to record our thanks to Dr. P. B. Ganguly and Prof. P. C. Sinha for their kind interest and ungrudging help and to the Vice-Chancellor of the Patna University for a research scholarship to one of us (R. B. N. S.) which enabled him to carry out this work.

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